

Pyridinium Bromocobaltate as a mild New Reagent for Bromination of Metal Acetylacetonates and its Normal Coordinate Analysis

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In our study of reactions of coordinated β -diketone ligands we have earlier reported the use of pyridinium bromochromate as a new brominating reagent for such chelates¹. Compared to *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS) not only the reaction time was much shorter but also the reactions occurred at ambient conditions unlike NBS which required drastic experimental condition of several hours of refluxing.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data conform to the molecular formulation as $(\text{PyH})^+(\text{CoO}_3\text{Br})^-$. The ir spectrum of the reagent displays bands at 3 200 (ν_{NH^+}), 1 600-1 588 ($\nu_{\text{C=N}}$, $\nu_{\text{C=C}}$), 1 510 ($\nu_{\text{C=C}}$, δ_{NH}), 1 465 (δ_{NH}), 1 435 ($\nu_{\text{C=C}}$), 1 310 ($\nu_{\text{C=C}}$) and 737 (pyridine ring deformation) which agree with literature values.

A comparison of the ionic part of the molecule, viz. $(\text{CoO}_3\text{Br})^-$ with $(\text{CrO}_3\text{F})^-$ of KCrO_3F and $(\text{CrO}_3\text{Cl})^-$ of KCrO_3Cl leads to the conclusion that the vibrational spectrum of pyridinium bromocobaltate is consistent with that expected of $(\text{CoO}_3\text{Br})^-$ ion as belonging to a C_{3v} point group of the XYZ_3 type ($X = \text{Co}$, $Y = \text{Br}$ and $Z = \text{O}$).

For a five-atom molecule of C_{3v} symmetry, six fundamental vibrations are expected and six modes are experimentally observed. The assignment of these vibrations of $(\text{CoO}_3\text{Br})^-$ is made in analogy with those reported for related compounds²⁻⁵. Co-Br stretching vibration frequency (ν_1) is fixed as 318 cm^{-1} . In XYZ_3 type the symmetric stretch of X-Z

bond has a lower frequency than the asymmetric stretch. Hence, the comparison with the related molecules assist to assign the 790 cm^{-1} as the Co-O symmetric stretching frequency (ν_2) and 855 cm^{-1} as anti-symmetric stretching frequency (ν_4). The deformation mode ν_3 is fixed as 218 cm^{-1} . The frequencies ν_5 and ν_6 are related to the bending modes of ZXY and ZXZ respectively. The band at 340 cm^{-1} is assigned to ZXZ (ν_6) bending with the band in the region of 170 cm^{-1} is expected for ν_5 . In all the related compounds it is found that $\nu_3 = (\nu_5 + \nu_6)/2$. This may be attributed to the combined deformation of the bond angles. This clue was taken to assume a value 170 cm^{-1} for ν_5 . The present work shows that the assignments lead to an acceptable set of molecular constants.

To confirm the assignments described, a normal coordinate analysis was carried out following Wilson's *F-G* matrix method using a general potential function along with potential energy distribution calculation. The calculated force constants are tabulated in Table 1. These have been utilised to evaluate valence mean square amplitudes. The stretching force constant f_D (Co-O) agrees well with the literature values³⁻⁵ (Table 1). The stretching force constants f_D (Cr-F) and f_D (Cr-Cl) are 3.36 and 2.00×10^{-2} N m^{-1} respectively^{4,5}. Hence, for f_D (Co-Br), the value is expected to be less and this view is supported by the value 1.69×10^{-2} N m^{-1} . This value is very close to the stretching force constant f_D (Cr-Br) calculated for PBC by earlier workers³ which is

TABLE 1—NORMAL CO-ORDINATE ANALYSIS RESULTS OF PBCo AT 298.16 K

Parameter	$D(X-Y)^*$ $d(X-Z)^*$	dd Dd	α θ	$a\theta'$ $\alpha\alpha$	$d\alpha'$ $d\alpha''$	$D\alpha$ $d\theta'$
Force constants ($f \times 10^2 \text{ N m}^{-1}$)	1.6924	0.1911	0.1362	-0.0081	-0.0412	-0.0420
Vibrational mean square amplitudes (bonded) ($\sigma \times 10^{-3} \text{ \AA}^2$)	5.4120	0.1046	0.0754	-0.0351	0.0265	-0.1214
Non-bonded mean square amplitudes ($\times 10^{-3} \text{ \AA}^2$)	3.6216	-0.0850	12.9877	3.9022	0.4104	0.8827
	1.6504	-0.1315	25.2611	0.4186	-0.2116	0.2475
	σ_p	σ_q	σ_{dp}	σ_{dp}	σ_{dq}	
Mean amplitudes (\AA)	11.6751	7.2058	0.8346	1.2674	0.9571	
	$I_D(X-Y)$	$I_d(X-Z)$	$I_p(Y..Z)$	$I_q(Z..Z)$		
	0.0601	0.0406	0.1269	0.0846		

*X = Co; Y = Br; Z = O.

$1.66 \times 10^{-2} \text{ N m}^{-1}$. The mean amplitudes of vibration (Table 1) for the bonded and non-bonded distances are characteristic and compare well with the earlier values⁶.

The acetylacetonates of Cr^{III} , Co^{III} , Cu^{II} , Co^{II} and Mn^{II} undergo bromination giving only the nucleophilic substituted bromo products of the composition $[\text{MBr}_4][\text{PyH}]_2$. In the case of Cu^{II} , the product is formed even at room temperature. The IR spectra of the bromo products derived from Co^{III} and Cr^{III} acetylacetonates display bands at 3030–3100 ($\nu_{\text{H-H}^+}$), 1620 (δ_{NH}), 1590 ($\nu_{\text{C=N}}$) and 750 cm^{-1} (pyridine ring def.), confirming the presence of pyridinium moiety in the brominated products. Ni^{II} and Zn^{II} acetylacetonates in acetic acid medium do seem to react with PBCo by an obvious change of colour leading to an ultimate green colour for the solution. However, no isolable product could be obtained.

Experimental

IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and Raman spectra on a Spex spectrometer attached with 3W argon ion laser (Spectra Physics).

Preparation of PBCo: Cobalto-cobaltic oxide prepared from cobalt nitrate (7.28 g, 0.04 mol) was refluxed with 48% HBr (50 ml) on a water-bath for 1 h. Upon addition of pyridine (20 ml) and concentration a yellow precipitate was obtained which was washed with ethanol and vacuum-

dried (yield 90.6%). The melting point was not sharp and the product was found air-sensitive. Longer exposure to air led to a change in the colour, the product becoming green and less effective as a reagent. Magnetic moment of the reagent measured by the Gouy method was found to be 4.4 B.M.

Bromination of metal acetylacetonates of Co^{III} , Cr^{III} , Mn^{II} , Co^{II} and Cu^{II} by PBCo: An acetic acid solution of PBCo was added dropwise to the substrate dissolved in a small amount of acetic acid. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for a few minutes with occasional stirring. The completion of the reaction was evidenced from change in the colour of the contents from yellow to green. The solid product that separated was washed with the solvent and dried under reduced pressure.

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